

LEARNING LOOPS IN THE PUBLIC REALM

WP6. Learning Living Lab - Verona
T6.3. Co-design and evaluation of alternative solutions

Deliverable D 6.3b

REPORT ON THE CO-DESIGN AND EVALUATION OUTCOMES

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The first loop co-design phase of the Verona Looper Living Lab (LLL) took place between September 2018, when the first meeting on how to organise the workshops happened, and February 2019, when the implementation of the proposed solutions was done.

On the 12th of July 2018 there was the first transition moment when the data visualisation platform was presented, with a press conference, to spread the word that the platform was online and working. This online platform was the basis on which the co-design activity later took place. The Looper project then took a break during August 2019 as participants were on summer break. At the beginning of September 2019 there was a meeting between the Italian project partner in order to organise the workshop, and on the 5th of October 2018 the first workshop took place.

During the first workshop of the 5th of October 2018 about 20 people participated, this included some council-employed who were there to lay out the ideas of the Municipality and to discuss technical details of the ideas proposed by citizens. This workshop was also used to visualise the data with participants to have a feedback on the feasibility of the platform, but also to better understand if participants correctly understood the data shown. After the data visualisation there was an interesting moment of dialogue between participants which could express their thoughts on the real situation and the differences they found between the data they collected and their perception of the situation. The other activity done during the first workshop was a presentation of good practices that can be found around the world to implement small-low budget solutions to create aggregation spaces and reduce traffic related pollutants. After these activities the actual co-design started and the approach was that of using printed maps, transferable paper and projected Google Earth and Street Maps views to help participants in better visualising the areas. The idea was to concentrate on the places where the co-monitoring took place in order to mostly focus on the areas with the most data collected, this both because participants already thought of implementing mitigation solutions in these places and also to have more chances in seeing differences with the second co-monitoring campaign.

To conclude the first co-design workshop the co-design online tool was presented. This tool is a pre-set one by Urbanista, later embedded in the local Looper webpages, with a user-friendly interface and just few simple options to allow people proposing their ideas also outside the workshop's timings. To submit an idea it was mandatory to select a category (i.e. greenspaces or traffic/mobility for the Verona LLL), give the idea a short title, give the description of the idea and insert the name/nickname. Apart from this fields it was also possible to upload an image (which gave some issues as per a bug from the tool), to choose a position for the idea within the area of Verona Sud and to add the email, if the person wanted to be contacted. After submitting the idea was possible to see it on the map at the beginning of the page, if the position was added, and/or on the list right underneath the map itself.

The second workshop took place on the 17th of October 2018 about 15 people participated, and this included a couple of council-employed who also participated at the previous workshop. The workshop begun with a recap of what was done during the previous event, and all of the idea proposed the 5th of October were shown on the co-design online platform. This was also to tell participants that there actually was an open online storage to keep track of what they were doing within the framework of the project. After the recap of the previous meeting ended the organisers showed to participants the ideas added online after the first workshop, and a debate on the newly proposed ideas took place within the participants. Later on the face-to-face idea proposal continued from where it sopped on the previous workshop (on the first one about 7 out of 19 spots had been discussed) and some new ideas were brought to attention from new participants, but also by people who participated at the previous meeting. The workshop then ended with only a few places left to be discussed, and this gave space to explain to participants the third, and last, workshop would have focused on concluding the debated on the last few spots, checking ideas added on line and defining a maximum number of ideas which would be the most important to be implemented in order to take those to the policymakers to find the right way to implement these. This would also help in the analysis and evaluation of the chosen solutions to prioritize them from a research point of view.

The third workshop took place on the 31st of October 2018, again about 15 people participate with a couple of council employed. The first half of this last workshop took place as like in the second one: activities focused on the recap of previous meetings, discussion on new ideas added online and discussion on possible ideas for the last few places from the co-monitoring campaign left to be discussed. The second half of the workshop was then all about choosing top 15 ideas that participants thought were the most efficient and feasible from an objective point of view first and then from a citizen and policymakers' point of view. Because of this dialogue moment the Verona LLL didn't do the sustainable MCA analysis and moved straight forward to the MAMCA.

In the end 14 ideas were chosen to be analysed and then implemented, citizens asked to add a couple of ideas they knew could hardly be implemented in the framework of the Looper project. This was because they wanted to have an official track of their long-term requests.

As the Verona LLL case has such a wide area to cover, when researchers moved to the MAMCA tool there was the need to aggregate and generalise the ideas, this was because the MAMCA works on the comparison between ideas to be applied in the same place. That is why there was a shift from proposals, which were the 14 ideas chosen with the workshops, to alternatives, groups of ideas that could be evaluated by the MAMCA tool.

The MAMCA evaluation considered three groups of stakeholders: citizens, Legambiente (NGO partner of the project) and local government (Comune di Verona part of the project). The criteria and weights given by each stakeholder was then evaluated by experts to give scores to the alternatives compared to criteria and stakeholders proposing them. The final results of the evaluation gave the prioritising of which ideas to implement first. It was interesting to see how the MAMCA results were the same of the ones from the confrontation from the last workshop.

The second loop co-design phase of the Verona Looper Living Lab (LLL) took place between July 2019, when the initial co-design meeting happened, and January 2020, when the first proposed solution for implementation was publicly presented in a press conference made by the Comune di Verona.

The first co-design workshop took place on the 3rd of July 2019, and about 20 people participate. This was supposed to be a workshop to define with participants how to face the second loop, based on the data collected during the monitoring campaign. Participants were not fully satisfied with the low impact of the ideas implemented within the first loop. For this reason, they were still keen to work on the criticalities already found during the first loop. Consequently, the meetings of the second loop focused mainly on the co-design activity and only part of them were dedicated to the problem identification.

This first meeting then was based on the data from the monitoring activity (measuring of air pollution and noise pollution after the implementation of selected mitigations solutions of the first loop). After discussing the monitoring results, it was decided to shift to the co-design of longer-term solutions (instead of small and isolated solutions), that could also work as pilot cases to be further replicated within the urban environment. This did not mean that participants abandoned what was done during the first loop, but rather that they re-designed such implemented ideas with a better community vision on the issues. During this first meeting it was defined what ideas were to be further implemented, and it was started to define how to implement them. By the end of the meeting it was decided to wait longer before a second workshop, to better visualise data and understand if this approach could be the right one. This activity was left free for the participants to make.

The second workshop was done on the 4th of December 2019, and participants confirmed that they wanted to continue with what said during the previous meeting. Furthermore, they told organisers that they were ready to better explain their concepts for the implementation of the four proposed solutions:

- creation of aggregation spaces through the closure of neighbourhood streets;
- creation of an urban forest in compartments 1 and 2 near Parco Santa Teresa;
- create a dialogue with Autostrade per l'Italia S.p.A. about possible noise reduction systems;
- further implementation of crosswalk islands.

The work done during the workshop was that of refining the ideas, with the help of the technical expertise of some employee from the Comune di Verona, and it was set a draft of the official document to be presented by the organisers to policymakers. By the end of the meeting, participants asked to

organisers to make a final version of the document in order to book an official meeting with policymakers. This meeting was to check if policymakers would endorse the proposed ideas within the agenda of the Comune di Verona, and organisers had to then report to the Verona Looper Living Lab the outcome of this meeting.

On 19th of December 2019 the organizers of Living Labs had a meeting with policymakers to illustrate some of the ideas produced by the Living Lab. It was a successful moment of sharing since the administrators accepted the proposed ideas, and they defined that each idea was to be officially presented with a press conference as soon as the main timing would be defined. On the 3rd of January 2020 the first idea about the expansion of Parco Santa Teresa with an urban forest was announced.

Due to the Covid-19 pandemic the second loop implementation is now (July 2020) on hold, with the aim of continuing the work to be able to implement the selected ideas.

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1. INTRODUCTION

For what it concerns the Verona LLL the first loop co-design phase went straight forward after the data visualisation as participants were willing to go further in the process of the Looper project. During the first loop co-design stage 38 possible implementation solutions were proposed and 14 were selected to be evaluated.

The second loop co-design stage was then a continuation of the work done within the first loop. To the 14 solutions already selected during the first loop, the following other solution - that was one of the 38 previously presented during the first loop - was considered:

- creation of an urban forest in compartments 1 and 2 near Parco Santa Teresa.

Due to the Covid-19 outbreak, and the lockdown period that went from March 2020 to June 2020, the project has been extended until the end of October 2020. Therefore this document, written in July 2020, will be further integrated as soon as the Verona Living Lab face-to-face meetings will start again.

1.1.Objective of D6.3b

The object of this deliverable is to describe and summarise the outcomes of the co-design and evaluation phase in both the first and second loop of the Looper Living Lab in Verona. This document is the continuing of deliverable D6.2b on the Verona Living Lab outcomes of the problem identification phase, as well as input from the meetings that took place in Verona.

1.2.Related deliverables

Deliverable D6.3b is final report that finalises deliverable D6.3a with the findings from the second loop. Similar deliverables will be written about the Looper Living Labs in Brussels and Manchester in work packages 5 and 7, respectively.

2. PLANNING OF THE FIRST LOOP CO-DESIGN STAGE

The planning of the workshops for the co-design stage took place during the first two weeks of September 2019, when the Italian partners (University Iuav of Venice, Legambiente and Comune di Verona) met to find a common approach for the activities to do with participants. During the partners' meetings it was possible to decide to add a collective data visualisation to begin with the first co-design workshop, in order to check if participants could use it and could understand the data collected in it.

It was also decided that, in order to gain the best result, during the first workshop we should have worked only with offline tools (i.e. printed maps, street view projections, talking and discussions, tracing paper) as the online co-design was not yet presented. It was also decided to present, during the first workshop, not only the co-design online tool but also good practices for mitigation solutions which could be found abroad. This was meant to help participants better understand which was the purpose of the workshops and the actual possibilities within the Looper project.

The planning for the other workshops was to do a recap at the beginning of the workshop of what was done previously in order to allow new participants to acknowledge what happened until that point, but also to take stock of the situations with people who already participate to the other workshops.

Concerning the co-design online tool, it was decided that it would work both as online collector for the ideas of people who could not participate to face-to-face meeting, but also as online storage of the ideas proposed during the workshops. This was to allow the tool to depict a more complete situation of what happened during the workshops in the end. The co-design online tool is a pre-set one developed by Urbanista: it was chosen as it already had all the things needed by the project with a user-friendly interface and enough layout flexibility to be modified to be embedded in the local websites. The tools work with a form to be filled, some parts are mandatory others are not, and it give the opportunity to position the idea on a map if someone wants to propose something more specific. Ideas can then be seen, once submitted, both on a map or as a list.

It was also decided that at every workshop at least one representative of the Comune di Verona would attend to keep the dialogue with citizens hope, and to answer technical questions about the proposed ideas as needed. This was also to continue with the learning that citizens were going through, as by doing this they would collect always new knowledges on different topics related to the project.

Once the activities of the workshop were set up, the engagement strategy was once again decided. It was decided to use both online and offline advertising methods, this to reach already engaged participants as well as hard to reach groups, with the hope to have them participating in the activities. The advertisement took place by using:

- blog post on local website;
- newsletters;
- news on Legambiente and Comune di Verona websites;
- press conference;
- flyers;
- word of mouth.

3. FIRST LOOP CO-DESIGN STAGE

3.1. Co-design workshops

3.1.1. Workshop #1

The first workshop was advertised in both online (i.e. blog post on local website, newsletters, news on Legambiente and Comune di Verona websites) and offline (i.e. press conference, flyers and word of mouth) ways in order to reach the wider amount of people. These methods were quite effective as on the 5th of October 2018, date of the first workshop, about 20 people participate to the workshop. Out of the 20 people participating both citizens and council-employed were there to work together.

The workshop started with a presentation of the data visualisation platform, even if participants said they already checked the page to see the data they collected. It was explained that the timeline bar for the AirBeam data selection was recently added, and it was explained why it was needed. It was asked to participants if there was something they could not understand from the data visualisation in order to explain it.

Figure 1 Data visualisation platform presentation

Then good practices from around the world have been presented, this to show to participants that even with a low budget it is possible to make a space more liveable. This was linked to the request that some participants had already made about the will of having more aggregation spaces.

During this first workshop the methods used to collect the ideas proposed are:

- printed maps;
- transfer paper;
- Google Earth projection;
- Street View projections.

These methods were chosen as they were found to be effective during the first activities of the scoping of issues phase. This because transfer paper allows to work on printed maps, while having the chance

to propose multiple things on the same printed map by simply exchanging the transfer paper, and in the meantime the use of Google Earth and Street View allows to better understand the spaces and positions which can, at times, be unclear by just looking at a printed map.

Figure 2 Participants gathering around the table with the printed maps to start the co-design activity

During this first workshop the online co-design tool was not used, it was only explained its purpose and how to use it. This was done as during a face-to-face meeting it would have been confusing and restrictive to use such a simplified tool on the go. The tool is structured to be used in a more straight forward way, which doesn't suit an offline meeting with multiple people discussing about the topic. Participants showed a good interest in it as it would allow also people not participating to the offline meetings to add their ideas. It was explained to them that ideas proposed during the workshops, once in a more defined structure, would be added to the online tool to create a storage of the work they were doing within the workshops.

As it was decided to organise the proposing of the idea by discussing on the possible solutions in the different places where the monitoring took place, only 7 spots out of 19 were discussed during this first workshop.

3.1.2. Workshop #2

The second workshop was advertised as the first one, with the only difference that the press conference wasn't done. About 15 people participated to this workshop and again there were policymakers attending it to help participants in evaluating the possible technical difficulties of the ideas they were proposing.

The beginning of the workshop was a recap of what happened during the first one, with some time spent to go through the list of ideas proposed on the previous meeting and of the ones proposed on the online platform in the time between the two workshops.

After this activity participants went back on discussing about the possible solutions to be implemented in the places monitored which were not discussed on the previous workshop. The methods used to collect ideas were the same ones from the first workshop: printed maps, transferable paper, Google Earth and Street View projections.

Figure 3 Tables prepared with the printed maps for the co-design activity

Figure 4 Participants discussing on a possible idea

Again it was not possible to conclude the discussion and proposal for every place left, so it was decided to finish the discussion about the monitoring spots during the third workshop.

3.1.3. Workshop #3

The third workshop was advertised as the second one using both online and offline ways, but without having a press conference hosted by the Alderman for the Environment of the Comune di Verona. About 15 people participated at this workshop and again there were policymakers attending it.

Figure 5 Some of the participants before the start of the meeting

The beginning of the workshop was again a recap of what happened during the first and second one, this to help the few new people to better understand what happened previously, and there was some time spent to go through the list of ideas proposed on the previous meetings and of the ones proposed on the online platform.

The methods used to collect ideas were the same ones from the first and second workshop, as these were found to be the most effective.

The final part of the workshop was then focused on choosing the ideas to focus on, which were later analysed with the MAMCA. Participants defined that 15 was the right number of ideas to be chosen in order to better focus the resources given by the project: the ideas chosen took in consideration the implementation feasibility, the budget and the timing given by the project. Still some ideas which could not be implemented in the framework of the project were listed as participants wanted to have them on official papers for the future.

3.2. Online co-design activities

The online co-design tool collected, by the end of the co-design workshops, 37 ideas of which 11 were ones proposed during the face-to-face meetings. This means that 26 ideas were proposed directly in an online format and then discussed during the co-design workshops.

Citizens encountered some issues when trying to attach pictures to the ideas they were proposing, the solution found was that of having them send the pictures to the staff of University Iuav of Venice to upload them from the administrator page in a second moment. These issues were due to a bug in the Urbanista tool, which still hasn't been solved.

No online debate took place, as people were more willing to talk about the ideas when they met between the workshops, and later they were taking the discussion about the online ideas to the workshop.

One main use of the online co-design tool was that of using it as a storage of the ideas proposed during the workshops to keep track of the work done. This was possible as by the end of each workshops the proposed ideas already had a first main feasibility evaluation done with participants and council-employed in order to have a complete idea to be uploaded on the co-design online tool.

Figure 6 Co-design online tool used as storage for the ideas proposed during the face-to-face meetings

4. RESULTS OF THE FIRST LOOP CO-DESIGN STAGE

4.1. List of proposals and alternatives

The proposals and alternatives shown here emerged during the Verona LLL meetings with all stakeholders, which took place in October 2018 and went on with the MAMCA between November 2018 and January 2019. It is extremely important here to understand the difference between proposals and alternatives as this then gives a better comprehension of the MAMCA results: proposals are ideas proposed during the workshops, these are specific and localised ones; alternatives are group of proposals made to suit the boundaries given by the MAMCA online tool. This grouping was done as the MAMCA works on the base that the alternative solutions to be evaluate are to be implemented in the same location, and it is needed to choose which one to implement in that location. The Verona LLL has multiple ideas to be implemented in different locations, but grouping them allows to generalise their location in order to get correct results by the MAMCA online tool.

Figure 7 Map of the proposals position

PROPOSAL	ALTERNATIVE	WHERE	WHAT	IMAGE
1	30 km/h zone	Via Scopoli	As via Scopoli is a quite wide street, and as drivers here speed up making it unsafe for pedestrians and cyclist, citizens here ask to create a 30km/h zone with urban elements to oblige drivers to slow down to make the street safer.	
2	Trees implementation	Via Scopoli	Implement the number of trees in the parking area in via Scopoli.	
3	Greenspaces	Via Scopoli	Transform in a public greenspace the small green area that can be found at the crossing between via Scopoli and Viale Fiera.	
4	Street closure	Via Ottavio Caccia	Close via Ottavio Caccia from the via Golosine side in order to create a safe pedestrian area where citizens can aggregate. The street will remain suitable for residents' vehicles only.	
5	Painting the streets	Via Santa Elisabetta	Via Santa Elisabetta is already a 30km/h zone. The proposal is to paint the street's asphalt in order to make more visible the already existing limit.	
6	Street closure	Via Monsignor Bellomi	Closing of the dead-end road to allow a more safe entrance/exit from the schools for children. Residents will still be allowed to pass by with vehicles at reduced speed.	

7	Islands for crosswalks	Via Colonnello Fasoli	Implementation of crosswalk islands outside the school with some urban furniture to slower passing cars and allowing children to have a safer crossing outside the school.	
8	Islands for crosswalks	Via Vigasio	Implementation of crosswalk islands to avoid dangerous overtaking and speeding as via Vigasio is a quite large and long straight road.	
9	Cycle lanes	Via Udine/Via Redipuglia	Implementation of the cycle lanes, where missing, in order to create a complete and continuous path for cyclists.	
10	Street closure	Via Udine	Closure of via Udine at entrance/exit hours of schools. An extra would be to make via Udine a 30km/h zone.	
11	Trees implementation	Via Redipuglia	Implement the existing trees to create a more concrete barrier between the street and the school courtyard.	
12	Green barriers	Highway	Realise a complete green barrier on both sides of the A4 highway in the part which cuts through the area of South Verona.	
13	Street closure	South Verona	Street closures in different parts of South Verona on weekend days to create aggregation spaces, which are missing and wanted by citizens. This could be implemented in the framework of the Mobility Days promoted also with the Mobility Week by EU.	

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Businesses relocation

Former freight yard

Persuade logistic businesses in moving their activity to the area called Quadrante Europa, realised by the Municipality for this purpose. This would help to alleviate the heavy traffic that clogs the area nowadays.

Table 1 Proposals' list with corresponding alternative

5. EVALUATION OF SUSTAINABILITY IMPACTS FOR THE FIRST LOOP

In the Verona LLL the Sustainability MCA was not done and the analysis process moved straight to the MAMCA. This was because an informal Sustainability MCA actually took place within the last workshop with participants, during which participants and policymakers discussed the feasibility of the proposed ideas to better decide on which to focus.

After this first moment of dialogue a set of 14 proposals were officially handled to the Comune di Verona by participants to evaluate the feasibility/sustainability of the options and the offices later sent the list of proposals to the district councils to collect their opinion and any further comment.

The first proposals to be implemented after this process were to be the ones with positive opinion by all stakeholders and participants.

6. EVALUATION OF FIRST LOOP SOLUTIONS WITH MAMCA METHOD

6.1. List of alternatives

In the frame of the procedure for the MAMCA analysis the list of alternatives shows the generic groups in which the proposals have been grouped together. The proposals, shown in the next section, have not been used for the evaluation made by experts as they used the alternatives listing.

ALTERNATIVES	PROPOSAL
STATUS QUO	/
30KM/H ZONE	1
GREENSPACES	3
TREES IMPLEMENTATION	2, 11
STREET CLOSURE	4, 6, 10, 13
PAINTING THE STREETS	5
ISLANDS FOR CROSSWALKS	7, 8
CYCLE LANES	9
GREEN BARRIERS	12
BUSINESSES RELOCATION	14

Table 2 List of alternatives

ha el

6.2. List of stakeholders

Stakeholder group	Definition	Representative	Details
<i>Name of the stakeholder group.</i>	<i>Description of the stakeholder group.</i>	<i>Name of person(s) interviewed.</i>	<i>Position of the person.</i>
Citizens	Residents of the area of Verona Sud	The survey was taken by many people together	
Legambiente	Verona section of a National NGO which operates to solve environmental issues	Chiara Martinelli	President of the Verona section
Comune di Verona	Municipality of Verona	The survey was taken by all the offices together	

6.3. Description of the MAMCA method

Description of what MAMCA is and how it was executed. Who were interviewed? How were stakeholders selected? How did stakeholders select their criteria? How did the stakeholders/citizens enter weights? See deliverable 3.3.

6.4. Evaluation of the alternatives according to citizens criteria

6.4.1. Criteria weights given by citizens

CRITERIA NAME	WEIGHT (%)
ROAD SAFETY	10.70%
QUALITY OF SPACES	9.73%
AIR QUALITY IMPROVEMENT	39.26%
NOISE REDUCTION	5.16%
TRAFFIC REDUCTION	35.14%

Table 3. Citizens' criteria weights

6.4.2. Expert evaluation of the impact of criteria on alternatives

This table shows the results and scores obtained from the evaluation made by experts (i.e. university professors in environmental technical physics and architects) on the criteria chosen by citizens..

The experts could choose an option between “very negative – slightly negative – negative – neutral – positive – slightly positive – very positive” to evaluate the impact of a certain alternative, when talking of a specific criteria and of a certain stakeholder.

Experts made the evaluation without knowing the weights given by citizens to the criteria to obtain the most objective result. Criteria weights given by citizens were then considered by the MAMCA tool itself in the final result.

ALTERNATIVES	ROAD SAFETY	QUALITY OF SPACES	AIR QUALITY IMPROVEMENT	NOISE REDUCTION	TRAFFIC REDUCTION	EVALUATION SCORE
STATUS QUO	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	0.000000
30KM/H ZONE	Positive	Slightly Positive	Slightly Positive	Slightly Positive	Slightly Positive	0.811070
GREENSPACES	Neutral	Very Positive	Slightly Positive	Slightly Positive	Neutral	0.546182
TREES IMPLEMENTATION	Neutral	Very Positive	Positive	Slightly Positive	Neutral	0.807925
STREET CLOSURE	Very Positive	Very Positive	Slightly Positive	Positive	Very Positive	1.152876
PAINTING THE STREETS	Positive	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	0.071363
ISLANDS FOR CROSSWALKS	Very Positive	Positive	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	0.218369
CYCLE LANES	Very Positive	Positive	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	0.218369
GREEN BARRIERS	Neutral	Positive	Slightly Positive	Slightly Positive	Neutral	0.470538
BUSINESSES RELOCATION	Very Positive	Very Positive	Positive	Positive	Very Positive	1.414620

Table 4 Experts' evaluation

6.4.3. Criteria weights analysis

Figure 1 Criteria weight analysis. This graph shows the weights of the citizens' criteria. The two most important criteria are air quality improvement (39.26%) and traffic reduction (35.14%). Road safety, quality of spaces, and noise reduction were given less weights by citizens

6.4.4. Criteria evaluation radar chart

Figure 8 Criteria evaluation radar chart. This graph shows how important are the different proposals when compared with the criteria weights given by citizens

6.4.5. Criteria group evaluation line/bar chart

Figure 9 Criteria group evaluation line/bar chart This graph shows the evaluation of the proposals based on the criteria weights given by citizens (bar chart) compared with the results of the evaluation done by experts (line chart). It can be seen how not always the desires solution proposed by citizens are in line with the experts evaluation (i.e. painting the streets)

6.4.6. Evaluation and weight chart

Figure 10 Evaluation and weight chart. This graph shows the overall combination of the criteria weights (line chart) compared with the evaluation score given by experts (line chart) on the base of both criteria and proposals. In fact here each coloured line is equal to one of the proposals, and is compared with both criteria, experts' evaluation and stakeholder criteria weights

6.5. Evaluation of the alternatives according to Legambiente criteria

6.5.1. Criteria weights given by Legambiente

CRITERIA NAME	WEIGHT (%)
AIR QUALITY IMPROVEMENT	23.92%
TRAFFIC REDUCTION	62.37%
NOISE REDUCTION	2.19%
GREENING IMPLEMENTATION	4.05%
SLOW MOBILITY IMPROVEMENT	7.48%

Table 5. Legambiente's criteria weights

6.5.2. Experts evaluation of criteria and alternatives

This table shows the results and scores obtained from the evaluation made by experts (i.e. university professors in environmental technical physics and architects) on the criteria chosen by Legambiente.

The experts could choose an option between “very negative – slightly negative – negative – neutral – positive – slightly positive – very positive” to evaluate the impact of a certain alternative, when talking of a specific criteria and of a certain stakeholder.

Experts made the evaluation without knowing the weights given by Legambiente to the criteria to obtain the most objective result. Criteria weights given by Legambiente were then considered by the MAMCA tool itself in the final result.

ALTERNATIVES/ CRITERIA	AIR QUALITY IMPROVEMENT	TRAFFIC REDUCTION	NOISE REDUCTION	GREENING IMPLEMENTATION	SLOW MOBILITY IMPROVEMENT	EVALUATION SCORE
STATUS QUO	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	0.000000
30KM/H ZONE	Slightly Positive	Slightly Positive	Slightly Positive	Neutral	Slightly Positive	0.775315
GREENSPACES	Slightly Positive	Neutral	Slightly Positive	Very Positive	Neutral	0.290539
TREES IMPLEMENTATION	Positive	Neutral	Slightly Positive	Very Positive	Neutral	0.450006
STREET CLOSURE	Slightly Positive	Very Positive	Positive	Slightly Positive	Very Positive	1.299814
PAINTING THE STREETS	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Slightly Positive	0.058145
ISLANDS FOR CROSSWALKS	Neutral	Slightly Positive	Neutral	Neutral	Slightly Positive	0.543227
CYCLE LANES	Neutral	Positive	Neutral	Neutral	Very Positive	0.809265

ALTERNATIVES/ CRITERIA	AIR QUALITY IMPROVEMENT	TRAFFIC REDUCTION	NOISE REDUCTION	GREENING IMPLEMENTATION	SLOW MOBILITY IMPROVEMENT	EVALUATION SCORE
GREEN BARRIERS	Slightly Positive	Neutral	Slightly Positive	Slightly Positive	Neutral	0.268058
BUSINESSES RELOCATION	Positive	Very Positive	Positive	Slightly Positive	Positive	1.434361

Table 6 Experts' evaluation

ha el

6.5.3. Criteria weights analysis

Figure 11 Criteria weight analysis. This graph shows the weights of the Legambiente's criteria. The most important criteria is traffic reduction (62.37%). Air quality improvement, noise reduction, greening improvement and slow mobility improvement were given less weights by Legambiente

6.5.4. Criteria evaluation radar chart

Figure 12 Criteria evaluation radar chart. This graph shows how important are the different proposals when compared with the criteria weights given by Legambiente

6.5.5. Criteria group evaluation line/bar chart

Figure 13 Criteria group evaluation line/bar chart. This graph shows the evaluation of the proposals based on the criteria weights given by Legambiente (bar chart) compared with the results of the evaluation done by experts (line chart). It can be seen how not always the desires solution proposed by Legambiente are in line with the experts evaluation (i.e. painting the streets)

6.5.6. Evaluation and weight chart

Figure 14 Evaluation and weight chart. This graph shows the overall combination of the criteria weights (line chart) compared with the evaluation score given by experts (line chart) on the base of both criteria and proposals. In fact here each coloured line is equal to one of the proposals, and is compared with both criteria, experts' evaluation and stakeholder criteria weights

6.6. Evaluation of the alternatives according to local government criteria

6.6.1. Criteria weights given by local government

CRITERIA NAME	WEIGHT (%)
COST	26.75%
AIR QUALITY IMPROVEMENT	3.79%
IMPLEMENTATION FEASIBILITY	26.75%
IMPLEMENTATION RAPIDITY	26.75%
QUALITY OF SPACES	12.16%
NOISE REDUCTION	3.79%

Table 7. Local government's criteria weights

6.6.2. Experts evaluation of criteria and alternatives

This table shows the results and scores obtained from the evaluation made by experts (i.e. university professors in environmental technical physics and architects) on the criteria chosen by the local government.

The experts could choose an option between “very negative – slightly negative – negative – neutral – positive – slightly positive – very positive” to evaluate the impact of a certain alternative, when talking of a specific criteria and of a certain stakeholder.

Experts made the evaluation without knowing the weights given by the local government to the criteria to obtain the most objective result. Criteria weights given by the local government were then considered by the MAMCA tool itself in the final result.

ALTERNATIVES/ CRITERIA	COST	AIR QUALITY IMPROVEMENT	IMPLEMENTATION FEASIBILITY	IMPLEMENTATION RAPIDITY	QUALITY OF SPACES	NOISE REDUCTION	EVALUATION SCORE
STATUS QUO	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	0.000000
30KM/H ZONE	Very Positive	Slightly Positive	Very Positive	Very Positive	Slightly Positive	Slightly Positive	0.817131
GREENSPACES	Very Negative	Slightly Negative	Neutral	Very Negative	Very Positive	Slightly Positive	-0.290038
TREES IMPLEMENTATION	Negative	Positive	Neutral	Negative	Positive	Slightly Positive	-0.045427
STREET CLOSURE	Very Positive	Slightly Positive	Positive	Very Positive	Positive	Positive	0.761342
PAINTING THE STREETS	Slightly Positive	Neutral	Very Positive	Very Positive	Neutral	Neutral	0.594485
ISLANDS FOR CROSSWALKS	Slightly Negative	Neutral	Positive	Positive	Positive	Neutral	0.286414

ALTERNATIVES/ CRITERIA	COST	AIR QUALITY IMPROVEMENT	IMPLEMENTATION FEASIBILITY	IMPLEMENTATION RAPIDITY	QUALITY OF SPACES	NOISE REDUCTION	EVALUATION SCORE
CYCLE LANES	Very Negative	Neutral	Slightly Negative	Very Negative	Very Positive	Neutral	-0.421580
GREEN BARRIERS	Negative	Slightly Positive	Positive	Negative	Positive	Slightly Positive	0.111844
BUSINESSES RELOCATION	Slightly Positive	Positive	Negative	Very Negative	Very Positive	Positive	-0.014750

Table 8 Experts' evaluation

ha el

6.6.3. Criteria weights analysis

Figure 15 Criteria weight analysis. This graph shows the weights of the local government's criteria. The three most important criteria are cost (26.75%), implementation feasibility (26.75%) and implementation rapidity (26.75%). air quality improvement, quality of spaces and noise reduction were given less weights by local government

6.6.4. Criteria evaluation radar chart

Figure 16 Criteria evaluation radar chart. This graph shows how important are the different proposals when compared with the criteria weights given by local government

6.6.5. Criteria group evaluation line/bar chart

Figure 17 Criteria group evaluation line/bar chart. This graph shows the evaluation of the proposals based on the criteria weights given by local government (bar chart) compared with the results of the evaluation done by experts (line chart). It can be seen how not always the desires solution proposed by the local government are in line with the experts evaluation (i.e. business relocation)

6.6.6. Evaluation and weight chart

Figure 18 Evaluation and weight chart. This graph shows the overall combination of the criteria weights (line chart) compared with the evaluation score given by experts (line chart) on the base of both criteria and proposals. In fact here each coloured line is equal to one of the proposals, and is compared with both criteria, experts' evaluation and stakeholder criteria weights

6.7. Multi-actor analysis

The results given by the MAMCA allows to make a comparison between the stakeholders and the evaluation scores referred to their criteria and weights. [Figure 19](#), here shows the preferences of the stakeholders on the same alternative, as each line refers to a specific alternative that then recalls the group of proposals.

Figure 19 Multi-actor analysis results compared with a base line on the status quo of the situation nowadays

6.8. Conclusions

With the MAMCA analysis it was possible to evaluate the interests of the different group of actors who decided to participate into the Looper project:

- Citizens: this group comprises a quite good variety of people with different cultural/social/educational/working backgrounds;
- Legambiente: an NGO devoted in the environmental preservation;
- Local government: the Municipality of Verona itself is a project partner.

What is missing here are businesses associations who were called to participate in the project but preferred not to participate. One of the aims for the second loop is to find a way to involve businesses into the project to have a more complete MAMCA analysis.

The evaluations shown in this document, as abovementioned, were not made by stakeholders. Experts were called to evaluate the criteria which describe the different needs, and later the system included the weights given by stakeholders to obtain the final results. This made it possible to objectively evaluate what was said by experts and what was said by stakeholders.

The results of the MAMCA analysis show the solutions which should encounter more approval from all stakeholders in the possibility of improving, and implementing, 30km/h zones in the area of South Verona. This because it is seen as a quick solution to begin with, and which can have multiple benefits such as: pollution reduction; street safety implementation; creation of aggregation spaces for children.

Another proposed alternative which encountered a mutual agreement in between the stakeholders is that of realising crosswalk islands to implement the safety of the streets in front of the schools. This solution was already in the Municipality business plan and it was autonomously proposed by citizens associations as well. This was an example of why a more strict dialogue channel is needed between citizens and policymakers.

To conclude the third commonly approved solution is that of the street closure. This proposal can have different declinations such as: all week street closure; weekends only street closure; closure only for entrance/exit from the schools hours. The local government is the stakeholder which pinpoints that the alternative is not always feasible, as it is not always possible to rearrange the mobility of the neighbourhood to permanently close a street. Nevertheless, they claimed to be open to a dialogue to see what it is possible to do as they would like to create aggregation centres for the community in the area of South Verona.

Figure 20 Preferred alternatives

7. ASSESSMENT OF THE EVALUATION PROCESS FOR THE FIRST LOOP

1. How did stakeholder selection take place? Who was responsible for the selection?

There was no stakeholders selection for citizens, the ones who were willing to help in the evaluation process answered at the MAMCA survey.

The other two stakeholders called to participate in the MAMCA process, Legambiente and local government, are project partners and already accepted to take part to it since the very beginning.

2. How easy was it to engage stakeholders to participate in the evaluation process? What was the cause of this?

Engaging citizens in the evaluation process was not easy, this because they could not completely understand why it had to be done as there was already enough discussion on the topic from their point of view.

3. Do you believe stakeholders understand the methodology behind MCA and MAMCA?

They do not completely understand the methodology behind MCA and MAMCA as it a tool meant to be used by researchers. Because of this the Italian partners will make a press conference and a meeting with participants during April 2019 to better clarify the topic.

4. Do you believe stakeholders trust the methodology behind MCA and MAMCA?

Citizens do not trust MCA and MAMCA as they could not completely understand it. In the same way Legambiente and the local government were not completely sure about the results as neither they could completely understand the methodology.

5. Do you believe the sustainability MCA and MAMCA had an impact on the selection of the alternative(s) that will be implemented?

As the sustainability MCA did not tool place we'll only consider the MAMCA. From the stakeholders point of view the results obtained from the MAMCA were the same which came out from the workshops and meetings. In this sense MAMCA was useful as chosen solutions got enforced by an objective tool which compared stakeholders needs and desiderata with experts' technical knowledge and evaluation.

only used to refute what was done until that moment.

6. Does MCA and MAMCA add extra value to the co-creation process?

For the Verona LLL case it did not add extra value in the choosing of the solutions to be implemented as we have different solutions in different places, while to use the MAMCA to its best it is needed to consider all of the proposed ideas as implemented in the same location.

On the other hand, MAMCA added extra value from the researchers point of view to get, as well as a problem framing, also a solution framing. This solution framing was due to the need of grouping the different proposals into alternatives in order to use the tool, and the work of finding the essential elements which compose the solutions are extremely important to better setup the second loop and the second co-design activity.

7. What would you improve if you had to do another evaluation using MCA and MAMCA?

The software is not completely user friendly as in the MAMCA version the pairwise comparison needs to be done on paper by stakeholders and then researchers need to import it in the system, in order not to give the password to everyone. The same thing goes for the experts' evaluation work. It would be interesting to have implemented in the software the justification experts needs to give to their evaluation, this to have a single collection point of everything concerning the MAMCA process.

8. Do you believe the online MAMCA software was useful?

For the Verona LLL it was not useful from a stakeholders proposal choosing point of view, but the software itself was useful for researchers as it is more user-friendly than doing the MAMCA in an offline version.

9. How easy was it to weigh the criteria of stakeholders?

The process of entering data to weight the criteria was easy, this because the online tool itself was user-friendly for researchers. Explaining to stakeholders the criteria weight process was not as easy, this because, in most cases, they were not completely able to prioritize criteria.

10. How easy was it to evaluate the impact of alternatives on criteria?

Experts found it sometimes difficult to evaluate the impact as different alternatives were located in different positions. Meaning that even though researchers grouped proposed ideas into more generic alternatives, sometimes it was not possible to evaluate the alternative without considering where to implement it later. For the second loop it will be needed to find a better way to group proposals into alternatives in order to avoid this problematic.

11. How easy was it to use and explain visuals/results from the online MAMCA software?

It was not easy to use and explain visuals/results from the online MAMCA software as it is too technical for someone who haven't used it before.

8. SUMMARY ABOUT THE FIRST LOOP IMPLEMENTATION

After the MAMCA analysis the process moved forward to the stage “3. Implementation and monitoring”. In the Verona LLL the implementation of the proposed solution took place from January 2019 and is still going on for one of the solutions (this document is written in July 2019). The solutions implemented before the second co-monitoring campaign are:

1. implementation of a temporary crosswalk island that will be later converted into a permanent one (Via Colonnello Fasoli);
2. closure of one street to create an aggregation space (Via Ottavio Caccia).

The co-monitoring campaign took place between February 2019 and April 2019, covering the same timeframe (February – April 2019) of the first co-monitoring campaign and collecting data throughout the implementation period.

The first results about the implementation are more qualitative observation gained since the beginning of the implementation as the official data from the second co-monitoring campaign are only partially uploaded on the data visualisation page and the analysis of the data with the citizens will not take place until the beginning of September 2019.

The implementation of temporary crosswalk gained some positive (direct) and less positive (indirect) feedback. The aim of the implementation was that of creating a more secure space in front of a Primary School, this by obliging drivers to slow down in proximity of the crosswalk that children use for entrance and exit in mornings and afternoons. The main positive feedback was given by residents that actually found cars to slow down due to the presence of the signals and the island itself. As a noise box and passive sensors were positioned on a balcony right next to the crosswalk it will be possible to see if there are more tangible changes in the air quality and noise situation. The indirect negative feedback was due to the presence of the school bus stop that was moved to allow the building of the crosswalk island. The moving forward of the school bus stop actually now obliges children to walk for a couple of meters on the street - between the footpath and the bus itself – due to the presence of rails that protect the footpath in front of the school from the street itself. This minor issue can be easily solved by moving the school bus stop a couple meters forward towards the intersection and by removing the last piece of rail to allow children to get on and off the bus straight from the footpath.

Figure 21 Implemented crosswalk island in front of the Primary School

The other implemented idea was the closure of Via Ottavio Caccia to create an aggregation space to stimulate the willingness of citizens to reduce the use of cars and create new better habits. Unfortunately some misunderstandings and problems were faced during the implementation. Due to some bureaucratic issues, mainly linked to the difficulties in organising the implementation on a short period of time (idea chosen in December 2018 and implemented in 2019), the public feedback was not completely positive as the street was closed for just one day without surveillance to enforce the closure. The closure of the street for one day, overlapping with the “Mobility Day” events in the city centre, created some misunderstanding between the City Council and citizens, and later meetings were organised with both parties to solve the misunderstanding. Citizens later explained that they wanted a multiple-days closure of the street, and the City Council explained the bureaucratic issues that created the one-day only closure. It will be evaluated with the next loop if participants still want to keep going with this alternative solution, by organising more in advance the closure - to have enough time for the bureaucratic needs - or if they would rather prefer to focus on a different solution.

In conclusion it is possible to tell that in the Verona Living Lab, due to the wide application area, some issues linked to the paper work emerged during the process as many steps and evaluation by different local and neighbourhood bodies are needed. Despite these issues, and the few ideas implemented, it is now possible to see that all stakeholders are now more willing to listen to the point of views of other parties, meaning that the work done within the Looper project to open a communication line between different stakeholders is starting to work.

9. PLANNING OF THE SECOND LOOP CO-DESIGN STAGE

The planning of the workshops for the co-design stage started in June 2019, when the Italian partners (University Iuav of Venice, Legambiente and Comune di Verona) talked to find a common approach on the activities to do with participants. It was then decided to start with a collective data visualisation of the monitoring campaign from the first loop to understand if participants were satisfied about their implemented solutions, or if they wanted to move to something different.

It was also decided that, given the uncertainty about what participants would prefer to do, during the first workshop only offline tools (i.e. printed maps, street view projections, talking and discussions, tracing paper) were to be used. The planning for the other workshops was to do a recap at the beginning of the workshop of what was done previously to take stock of the situations.

It was decided to keep the good practice to have at least one representative of the Comune di Verona attending the workshops to answer technical questions. This was also to keep the learning process continue through the second loop as well.

The advertisement of this second loop took place by using:

- blog post on local website;
- newsletters;
- news on Legambiente and Comune di Verona websites;
- word of mouth.

10. SECOND LOOP CO-DESIGN STAGE

10.1. Co-design workshops

The co-design and implementation activities for the second loop of the Verona Looper Living Lab were put on hold due to the Covid-19 outbreak. Furthermore, the project deadline was extended until October 2020 to allow the completion of the last stages of the second loop.

10.1.1. Workshop #1

The first workshop was advertised in both online (i.e. blog post on local website and newsletters) and offline (i.e. word of mouth) ways in order to reach the wider amount of people. These methods were quite effective as on the 3rd of July 2019, date of the first workshop for the second loop, about 20 people participate to the workshop. Out of the 20 people participating both citizens and council-employed were there to work together.

The workshop started with a presentation of the data collected during the monitoring campaign uploaded on the visualisation dashboard (measuring of air pollution and noise pollution after the implementation of selected mitigations solutions of the first loop). Given the results from the visualisation of the monitoring campaign from the first loop, participants decided to skip the second scoping activity since the issues to work on were unchanged from the first loop. For the same reason, the monitoring activity from the first loop coincided and overlapped with the data collection for the second loop.

This decision was mainly due to the almost non-existent reduction of pollutants in the area after the first loop, and this made participants rethink about the whole process. Given the information gathered during the first loop, and after the implementation of small punctual solutions, they decided that it was better to focus on longer term solution - that can also keep the process going after the end of the project itself - and/or on solutions that can be further replied on a wider urban area.

Since during the first loop different longer-term ideas were not included in the process - despite the high consensus - because participants preferred to implement something more immediate, there was a different type of co-design activity for the second loop. Instead of proposing new ideas, participants

started to better discuss - and design - the already proposed ideas to allow their implementation in a real urban environment.

The main ideas re-introduced from the first loop were:

- the opportunity of designing the expansion of the Parco Santa Teresa to integrate an urban forest, and
- the opportunity of talking with Autostrade per l'Italia S.p.A. on how to reduce the highway noise impact on the neighbourhood.

Still something good came from the ideas implemented during the first loop. Participants requested to further implement the crosswalk island of via Fasoli by better re-placing the school bus stop, and they asked to implement some other crosswalk islands around the city to improve pedestrian's safety. Furthermore, since the street closures didn't work as participants expected - because of their implementation as solutions for "individuals", they decided that it would be better to find a way to transform the idea. To do so participants tried to better understand how to make a street closure a way to involve the whole community to better explain and promote better habits to live and move in urban areas, and how to organise a street closure event to make it replicable anywhere around the city.

The workshop was concluded with the commitment from participants to better define what were their desiderata about these ideas in order to write a proper presentation document to be handled officially to the Comune di Verona in order for them to endorse the solutions co-designed by the Verona LLL.

10.1.2. Workshop #2

The second workshop was advertised in the same way of the first one, and about 15 people participated to this workshop. Again, there were policymakers attending it to help participants in evaluating the possible technical difficulties of the ideas they were proposing.

The beginning of the workshop was a recap of what happened during the first one, and to check if participants still felt to continue as proposed during the previous meeting. This was done because of the time gap between the two meetings - the first one took place the 3rd of July 2019 and the second was on the 4th of December 2019. Since participants were still convinced about the planning done, this meeting was used to draft the official document to be handled to the Comune di Verona.

By the end of the meeting organisers were appointed to write the final version of the document, and to officially present it to the Comune di Verona, with the duty to report to the Verona LLL what said during the meeting with policymakers.

10.1.3. Workshop #3

A third workshop will be held before the end of the project in October 2020. The aim of this workshop (or multiple workshops) will mainly be to keep the cooperation strong between different stakeholders. This will be possible by updating participants on the timing to realise the proposed - and endorsed by the Comune di Verona - ideas, to allow the understanding that it is possible to continue the process on a long-term basis even after the official end of the Looper project itself.

10.2. Online co-design activities

There were no new solutions and ideas collected with the online co-design tool during the second loop, and it was due to the decision of develop and work on some of the longer-term ideas proposed during the first loop.

11. RESULTS OF THE SECOND LOOP CO-DESIGN STAGE

The document with the list of the 4 solutions developed during the Living Labs was presented by organizers to policymakers.

Hereafter a transcription of the requests officially presented to the Comune di Verona (translated in English).

1. Creation of aggregation spaces through the closure of neighbourhood streets

Possibility of creating aggregation spaces realised through temporary closures of some portions of streets and/or squares, which can then be evaluated as permanent pedestrianization.

This request wants to follow up, and wants to improve, what was proposed during the first loop of the project with the closure of Via Ottavio Caccia. It is therefore requested, following the constructive dialogue made with regard to the closure of March 2019, that the closure events are to be identified as pilot tests. The timing for these events should be of at least two consecutive days (ideally Saturday and Sunday), to be repeated weekly or monthly. The Verona LLL also proposes to involve residents and businesses in a more closer way, and to also contact possible associations in order to plan activities that can part of a wider process of re-appropriation of urban spaces.

This proposal aims to encourage the population to change their habits about how to live the neighbourhood, and in the choice of a more ecological mobility, thus allowing them to recreate a stronger sense of community.

The possible streets for these temporary events are:

- *Via Ottavio Caccia (4th Circumscription)*
- *Via Ghetto (4th Circumscription)*
- *Piazza dei Caduti (4th Circumscription)*
- *Via Centro (5th Circumscription)*
- *Via Scuderlando - direction south in front of the parish (5th Circumscription)*

It would also be possible to contact the following associations for the organization of activities during temporary closures:

- *Borgoroma welfare*
- *Interzone Association*
- *New Acropolis*
- *Vanguard*
- *La Genovesa Educational Farm*
- *Coop. Soc. onlus Energie Sociali*
- *APS Quartiere attivo (lessons on the history of neighbourhoods in Verona)*
- *Granbadò*
- *Generalab (co-working space managed by different associations)*
- *ALOUD*
- *Kroen*

For better results, it is therefore necessary to have a better control at access points during closures in order to take full advantage of these moments of neighbourhood space sharing.

2. Creation of a urban forest in compartments 1 and 2 near Parco Santa Teresa

With regard to the issue of the extension of the Parco Santa Teresa in the 4th district, the Looper Living Lab of Verona proposes the creation of a urban forest in compartments 1 and 2, in order to create a green lung for the city.

The request is that of creating this space of urban forest. This is to be understood as a pilot project that can be replicated in other areas of the city so as to benefit the entire population of Verona.

For example, other areas where it would be possible to replicate this intervention in the future are the former railway station and the space right underneath the Telecom tower in Via Scopoli.

3. Dialogue with Autostrade per l'Italia S.p.A.

Given the strong impact of the A4 motorway section that divides the Verona Sud area, the Verona LLL proposes to Comune di Verona to request, via official channels, a meeting with Autostrade per l'Italia S.p.A. during which, together with the Comune di Verona, the Looper Living Lab can participate. The

aim of this meeting is to evaluate alternative solutions for noise abatement, which can also be implemented with green barriers and/or planting solutions for the reduction of pollutants caused by the transit of vehicles.

4. Implementation of crosswalk islands

The Looper Living Lab of Verona also proposes that the pedestrian area in Via Colonnello Fasoli be redesigned and restored as per request of the Looper project itself in February 2019.

This crosswalk island had been implemented temporarily in front of the Primary School, but the position was not the most suitable. Because of this the Verona LLL requests to reposition it and make it permanent given the benefits in terms of safety for citizens.

After the successful presentation of the document to policymakers - that took place on the 19th of December 2019, the solution n°2 “Creation of a urban forest in compartments 1 and 2 near Parco Santa Teresa” was presented with a press conference on the 3rd of December 2020.

12. EVALUATION OF THE IDEAS FOR THE SECOND LOOP

There was no MCA or MAMCA analysis during the second loop of the Verona LLL. This can be explained since the ideas for the implementation were the ones already proposed during the first loop, and there was a common agreement on working on longer term solutions within participants.

13. SUMMARY ABOUT THE SECOND LOOP IMPLEMENTATION

After the co-design activity, the process moved straight to the stage “3. Implementation and monitoring”.

The Comune di Verona already officially accepted, and endorsed, the proposal about the urban forest with a press conference on the 3rd of January 2020. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic the three other proposed ideas were put on hold, but the work will start again after July 2020 to allow the endorsement of the other three ideas in the agenda of the Comune di Verona.

Figure 22 Co-designed idea for the long-term implementation of an urban forest

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